

Teaching Pragmatic Competencies as a Methodical Problem in Uzbekistan

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Abstract:

Traditionally, until recently, teachers in Uzbekistan mainly taught students language forms and grammar rules, but language function and language use were at the bottom of their lists, sometimes neglected. From the results of recent years of research in the field, it is clear that pragmatic competence cannot be developed by itself by inculcating grammatical rules in the learner. Indeed, there is a big difference between language form and language function and language use. The following article discusses these branches of the topic.

Keywords: pragmatics, speech acts, compliments, refusals, language form, language function.

Theoretically, because of different contexts, one language form can perform different language functions, and one language function can manifest itself in different language forms. For example, the sentence "The door is open" can be seen in various situations in the following functions:

- stating, explaining or reporting a fact;
- remind the listener to close the door when leaving;
- to let the listener know that he did not close the door;
- to say to tell the listener that the room is cold.

On the other hand, when asking the listener to close the door, it is possible to understand the following language functions based on the speaker's speech:

- 1) "Door!" (so as not to be seen by strangers)
- 2) "Close the door, please." (regarding)
- 3) "Will you close the door?" (offer)

4) "Do you want to close the door?" (knowing the listener's intention)

5) "You close the door" (advice or order)

While discussing the importance of developing pragmatic competence, several more questions do not give peace: can pragmatic competence be developed naturally by acquiring vocabulary and grammatical knowledge, or should pragmatic competence be taught? In general, is it possible to teach pragmatic competence?

In recent years, there has been increasing interest in teaching speech acts in English as a Second Language (ESL) and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes. Research has particularly focused on the effectiveness of various approaches to presenting a range of behaviors, including requests (Morrow, 1995; Rose, 1994; Takahashi, 2001), apologies (Olstein and Cohen, 1990; Tateyama et al. , 1997).), rejection (Morrow, 1995) and compliments (Billmeyer, 1990; Rose & Ng, 2001) speech acts have moved to the center of attention of the scientific community. However, despite the focus on how to teach them successfully, most teachers are still not convinced that speech acts should be taught, and those who want to do so seem unprepared to teach speech acts. In this work, we offer some practical criteria for teachers to use:

Is it necessary to teach speech act?

- What should students be able to do as a result of the lesson?
- Which resources are most effective in teaching speech acts?
- How to determine the effectiveness of the lesson?

Due to the universality of some pragmatic knowledge, foreign language learners can derive some principles from their native language in organizing speech; they may express their intentions implicitly, or they may use context to infer implicit meanings. However, educational psychologists have found that foreign language learners cannot easily apply all useful knowledge and strategies to foreign language learning. They recognize that it is easier to understand speech or discourse literally than to make free inferences from the context.

The concept that the promotion of pragmatic competence should begin with increasing the pragmatic awareness of both students and teachers has been at the center of many discussions. Kathleen Bardovi-Harlig argues that pragmatic awareness should be one of the goals of classroom instruction.

If both language learners and teachers realize the importance of pragmatic competence and are active in developing their pragmatic competence, they can make certain improvements in the teaching and learning process of English, as well as their pragmatic and there is a need to improve communicative competence.

First, we need to distinguish between language form and language function in learning and teaching English. Teachers should not be content with just teaching students large amounts of vocabulary and grammar; rather, it is important that they develop some speech situations to provide students with opportunities to use their language skills. Students are required to use all opportunities to apply what they have learned, linguistic or pragmatic knowledge. Secondly, when teaching English, teachers should pay attention to the context. In the above discussion, we have seen that the same sentence can have different meanings and functions in different contexts. It is important for teachers to help students understand the unique role of context in language use. Thirdly, teachers should develop students' sensitivity to cultural differences in English language teaching. People from different cultures can understand the same word differently. Thus, it is acceptable to recognize that culture plays a leading role in the formation of pragmatic competence by increasing pragmatic awareness. After all, language learning is, first of all, a process of developing pragmatic

competence. Different scholars have different opinions on the definition of pragmatic competence. D. Haymes (1972) first expanded the concept of competence proposed by N. Chomsky in the 1960s and then proposed the term communicative competence, which consists of four components: opportunity, application, appropriateness and reinforcement. In general, it is believed that the first component is equivalent to linguistic competence, and the other three components are subordinate to pragmatic competence.

J. Leach (1983) was the first to distinguish between pragma-linguistics and socio-pragmatics, so pragmatic competence is divided into pragma-linguistic competence and socio-pragmatic competence. The first involves the use of correct grammar and the appropriate language form to carry out a certain communication, and the second requires the speaker to follow the social rules of language use in order to engage in correct communication. Pragmatic competence is the ability to understand and use language correctly and appropriately in a specific context to achieve successful communication.

"Sociolinguistic competence" used by L. Bachman (1990) is also one of the main parts of communicative skills and mainly consists of socio-cultural rules of discourse.

Commenting on communicative skills, J. Leung (2005) recognizes two specific elements of communication skills. These include linguistic and phonological areas, as well as pragmatic skills that reveal the purposeful essence of the interlocutors or parties in the communication process.

It should be recognized that since the eighties of the 20th century, the teaching of foreign languages in Uzbekistan began to move from the theoretical stage to the practical stage. The issue of form (form) in language teaching is formed especially on the basis of grammatical principles, the dynamic feature of the language is communication, communicative competence is found in textbooks in the form of monologue or dialogue in many cases.

Despite the fact that the approach to teaching foreign languages has been fundamentally changed since the first years of independence, foreign language teachers and specialists themselves were not ready for these changes. At the end of the 90s, the functions of direct teachers in the teaching process increased. From the early years of the 20th century, teachers began to talk about the ineffectiveness of centralized lessons, the fact that the centralized method of training is no longer justified. Every time they returned to their classrooms, what they actually learned was not the same, and classroom activities reverted to traditional form-based language teaching.

As a solution to these complexities and problems in language teaching, CLT (language teaching based on communicative competence) and CEFR (European Language Teaching Standards) programs have become effective. In the classroom, creating a language environment between students and the teacher, the teacher is not just a dominant manager, but is directly reflected in the functions of assistant, guide, supervisor and assessor in the language teaching process.

Textbooks introduced in schools, colleges, and lyceums began to displace formative teaching traditions focused solely on teaching grammar and vocabulary while emphasizing oral and written, listening, and reading skills.

But the above achievements are still not perfect, today's era does not meet the requirements of language teaching one hundred percent, because modern language teaching skills at the same time form the student's critical thinking abilities (speech acts) is being put on the agenda. This makes it possible for them to be socially active and respond to life situations and issues. In general, how important is the inclusion of speech acts and pragmatic elements in the process of language teaching? Can speech acts be taught in the classroom? These questions are very relevant and relevant, and it is the goal of every teacher or specialist who enters the classroom to teach a foreign

language to carry out the characteristics of teaching speech acts in harmony with efficiency and receptive skills. must enter the duties.

In the process of teaching a foreign language in the classroom, a teacher or specialist should take into account the following aspects.

- rapport - positive formation of teacher-student relations; that pupil-student relations are organized in the status of mutual support,
- needs - studying the needs of students before the lesson, analyzing them, paying special attention to how well the subject being taught or being taught can satisfy these needs,
- materials - the student's age, psychology, interests, perspective views, cultural-ethnic aspects, vitality, time and space commonalities of the selected or selected materials in real situations,
- classroom seats - the location of desks and chairs during the training, during these locations, the students can see each other, the teacher, see the facial expressions of their interlocutors or partners when interacting, and observe their emotions. It is of fundamental importance that it is taken into account.

Including these principles, it is appropriate to teach students speech acts in harmony with speech skills. One of the tasks facing a foreign language teacher is to teach students communicative speech, which should be motivational, purposeful, situational, self-forming, and have an emotional color.

Already, there are some difficulties in teaching communicative speech at school: firstly, the personal characteristics of students and teachers, their linguistic experience in native and foreign languages; secondly, not all the used textbooks and materials devote enough space to the problem of teaching communicative speech. What attracts a child who starts learning a foreign language? First of all, the ability to communicate in a foreign language may attract their attention. The task of the teacher is to teach communication in a foreign language, and in this regard, to help students overcome the difficulties of teaching a foreign language.

Possible problems in learning speech can be categorized as follows:

- 1) students are embarrassed to speak a foreign language, are afraid of making mistakes and, thus, face criticism from the teacher and peers, or just because of this, they are shocked;
- 2) students' opinions and views on the discussed problem are shallow, because they do not have enough information on a specific topic in their native language;
- 3) students do not have enough language and speech tools to solve the problem, because of this, in most cases, instead of communicating in English in pairs and groups, students often use their mother tongue and make many mistakes.

Currently, the English language is a means of international communication, and the main goal of teaching is the formation of communicative competence. Thus, the main role is given to oral communication. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the teaching of communicative speech in the modern methodology of teaching foreign languages. Based on the above, we came to the conclusion that this topic is really relevant at the moment.

One of the main goals of English lessons is to study the possibilities of using educational and speech situations in the development of communicative and speech skills of students. Based on this plan, the following tasks are formed:

- analysis of the literature related to the research problem;
- to determine the influence of educational and speech situations on the development of students' communicative and speech skills in English classes;

- development of lesson parts using educational and speech situations in communicative and speech communication in English classes;
- justify the conditions of the effectiveness of using educational and speech situations in the development of students' communicative and speech skills in English classes.

We assume that the successful acquisition of language skills by students is possible with the successful use of educational and speech situations as a condition for the development of communicative and speech skills in students under the following conditions:

- the content of the foreign language teaching program taking into account the real information stock of the audience (real, conditional and problematic);
- the desire to make the process interesting with the help of verbal aids (diagrams, tables, plans with key words, supporting notes), as well as non-verbal aids (pictures, films);
- to analyze the problem of developing communicative and speaking skills of students in English classes.

Communicative speech communication is a specific form of speech, in which the following extra-linguistic features are manifested:

1. Summary of information.

Interlocutors should always have "interaction points in speech". When choosing partners for communication, the teacher should keep this in mind, take into account the commonality or closeness of their interests, awareness.

2. Possible diversity in the content and volume of information.

In natural communication, this ensures the development of communication. This parameter should be taken into account when developing situations for teaching communicative speech communication.

3. Evaluation of information.

When organizing training in communicative speech communication, it is necessary to choose replicas (clichés, speech formulas) for the adequate linguistic design of these reactions.

4. Influence of communication environment.

It is important to pay attention to where and under what conditions speech communication takes place. It also determines the choice of language tools, their organization to solve communicative tasks.

The communicative direction of teaching a foreign language assumes the role of a real communicator, which allows the student to act adequately in a communicative situation, regardless of the degree of limitation of practical goals. Therefore, this logical, reasonable requirement should be implemented in such a way that any limited vocabulary; any grammatical competence of the student is able to perform the tasks of exchange of ideas when applied according to a specific situation.

Language communication based on the knowledge of a foreign language also implies that the partners in speech communication follow the appropriate language and form of the situation. In this case, learning the language as a means of communication largely includes learning the skills to perform certain roles of communicators in the communication process in certain conditions. Usually, over all types of speech activity, including listening, speaking, reading, writing, the most natural form of speech activity is the oral form, in its main form, dialogue, without words, has priority.

The purpose of learning a foreign language is to use it in communication, that is, to develop the communicative competence of English language learners along with learning English. Pragmatic competence should be important in learning English because it is an important element of communicative competence.

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